

A Cognitive Approach to Metaphor Translation in Diplomatic Discourse from English into Arabic

ترجمة الاستعارة في الخطاب الدبلوماسي من اللغة الإنجليزية إلى اللغة العربية على ضوء المقاربة المعرفية

Chafik Haif Si Haif ¹, Ouissem Touati ²

¹ University of Algiers 2 Institute of Translation and Interpreting, chafik.sihaf@univ-alger2.dz

² University of Algiers 2 Institute of Translation and Interpreting, ouissem.touati@univ-alger2.dz

Reçu le:03/05/2022

Publié le:17/06/2022

Abstract

The present study takes a cognitive approach to metaphor and investigates how conceptual metaphors underlying the metaphorical expressions are used in English diplomatic discourse and explores how they are translated into Arabic. The objective of this study is to uncover the peculiarities and the major types of metaphor represented in diplomatic speeches as well as translation decisions between two unrelated languages and cultures, namely English and Arabic. The theoretical framework relies mainly on Lakoff and Johnson's (1980/2003) groundbreaking Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT) and Mandelblit's (1995) Cognitive Translation Hypothesis (CTH). The study is carried out employing a contrastive analysis by identifying the most frequent conceptual metaphors underlying metaphorical expressions in the source text and their equivalents in the target text, and comparing them on the basis of the two schemes proposed in Cognitive Translation Hypothesis, so as to determine whether the translator preserves and/or transforms the conceptual mapping of metaphors of the source text while translating them to the target text.

Keywords: Metaphor, Diplomatic Discourse, Conceptual Metaphor Theory, Cognitive Translation Hypothesis.

الملخص:

تهدف من خلال هذا المقال إلى تسليط الضوء على ترجمة الاستعارات التصورية الكامنة وراء التعبيرات الاستعارية في الخطاب الدبلوماسي من خلال المقاربة المعرفية. إذ تعد الاستعارة آلية مركزية في إنتاج الخطاب الدبلوماسي وفهم دلالاته وترجمته فضلا عن كونها أداة جمالية لخرافة الكلام. وتكمن أهمية هذا البحث في الكشف عن الخصائص والأنواع الرئيسية للاستعارة التي تتجسد في الخطاب الدبلوماسي وكذا كيفية التعامل معها عند ترجمتها من اللغة الإنجليزية إلى اللغة العربية. يعتمد الإطار النظري على نظرية الاستعارة التصورية التي اقترحها لايفكوف وجونسون (2003/1980)، وفرضية الترجمة المعرفية لماندلبلت (1995). وتم إجراء الدراسة التطبيقية من خلال تحليل ترجمات نماذج للاستعارات الأكثر شيوعاً في النص المصدر وما

يكافئها في النص الهدف، ومقارنتها على أساس المخططين المقترحين في فرضية الترجمة المعرفية، وذلك لتحديد ما إذا كان المترجم يحتفظ بنفس استعارات النص المصدر أثناء ترجمتها إلى النص الهدف.

الكلمات المفاتيح: الاستعارة، الخطاب الدبلوماسي، نظرية الاستعارة التصورية، فرضية الترجمة المعرفية

Introduction

In this era of globalisation, the translation and interpretation of diplomatic discourse has become an increasingly important area of research within the discipline of Translation Studies, and which presents a number of challenges. These include in general the sensitivity of the topics involved, the interdisciplinary nature of the field, and the particular conceptual and communicative constraints that affect the diplomatic translation/interpreting process.

It has been demonstrated that metaphor frequently appears in diplomatic discourse and is a prominent feature of diplomatic language. Therefore, its handling in translation is one of the major translation issues to be studied. Metaphor for most people is a linguistic ornamental device, which has some rhetorical and aesthetic purposes. However, in diplomatic discourse, metaphor has been proved to have more significant cognitive and communicative functions that are exhibited in the text. The role of metaphor in this sense is that it is used in shaping abstract and complex concepts and ideas in terms of concrete representations or experiences to make them more accessible for the audience. Therefore, understanding how speakers construct and communicate metaphors could be a great help for translators/interpreters in order to better understand and accurately convey their speeches.

The present study investigates the use of metaphor in English diplomatic discourse and its translation into Arabic from a cognitive perspective. Starting from the idea that metaphor is a conceptual phenomenon, and viewing it primarily as a matter of conceptualisation of topics and concepts, the study intends to answer the following research questions:

- What are the major types of conceptual metaphors identified in English diplomatic discourse?
- To what extent these conceptual metaphors are preserved and/or transformed in the Arabic target text?

Theoretical framework

Several research in metaphor studies and translation studies have been devoted to discussions on the issue of translatability of metaphorical expressions. Most of these debates were based on a traditional view of metaphor as a figure of speech and neglected the cognitive and communicative implications in discourse. This section attempts to discuss the implications of the cognitive view of metaphor for a better understanding of the issue of metaphor translation in diplomatic discourse.

I. Conceptual Metaphor Theory

For a long time, metaphor was viewed as a figure of speech that is used mainly in literary texts for ornamental and artistic purposes. However, the more recent cognitive approach to metaphor within cognitive linguistics, of which Lakoff and Johnson (1980) were the pioneers, brought about a paradigm shift in the study of metaphor. In their influential book *Metaphors We Live By* (1980/2003), the authors proposed Conceptual Metaphor Theory (CMT). Within this theory, metaphor is no longer seen as a pure matter of language and as a decorative element only, but also, and more importantly, as a matter of thought and conceptualisation, a crucial element that reflects the way humans think and communicate. Lakoff and Johnson (2003) argued that metaphor is pervasive in everyday language, and that the human conceptual system is inherently constructed by metaphorical terms: “Metaphors and linguistic expressions are possible precisely because there are metaphors in a person’s conceptual system” (Lakoff & Johnson, 2003, p.06).

From the point of view of CMT, Metaphorical expressions are actually the linguistic manifestation of deeper conceptual metaphors. Conceptual metaphor can be defined as understanding one domain of experience in terms of another domain of experience (Kövecses, 2017, p.14). Cognitive linguists use the term *source domain* to refer to the conceptual domain from which we draw metaphorical expressions, and *target domain* to denote the conceptual domain that we are trying to understand. The target domains are for the most part more abstract and therefore more difficult to conceptualise, whereas the source domains are typically more concrete and easily recognised because they derive mainly from peoples’ physical, social or cultural experience (Lakoff & Johnson, 2003, p.59). The relationship between the target domain and the source domain draws a correspondence or a *conceptual mapping* that is presented in this way: TARGET DOMAIN IS SOURCE DOMAIN. A wide range of metaphorical expressions are produced through the analogy between the meaning or the structure of source domain and that of target domain.

This can be illustrated in the conceptual metaphor TIME IS MONEY. In this case, TIME is the target domain, i.e. what we try to understand, and MONEY is the source domain, i.e. what we use in order to do so. This conceptual metaphor is reflected in metaphorical expressions such as ‘*spend your time*’, ‘*waste my time*’ and ‘*invest a lot of time*’ (Lakoff and Johnson, 2003, p.7-8). These metaphorical expressions are evidence that time is conceptualised as money, which enable us to speak of time being spent, wasted and invested, even though time itself is abstract and intangible.

Kövecses (2017) maintains that the application of a source domain to a specific target domain contributes to the construction of a certain reality that may affect our views of the world or even create new realities for us (p.17). Since metaphor involves constructing something in terms of something else, the choice of a particular source domain affects how the target domain is perceived or represented.

CMT allows us to explore metaphors at textual level instead of word level, which suits the purpose of this study.

II. Metaphor in diplomatic discourse

The developments of the cognitive approach to metaphor in recent years have opened the way for many studies on metaphor and is no longer confined to the field of literary language as the traditional theories indicate, but also in many other fields and discourse types. As the research field of this study focuses on diplomatic discourse, it is necessary to understand the peculiarities of metaphor in this specific type of discourse.

It could be argued that the use of metaphor is particularly essential in the discourse of diplomacy and international relations since they are abstract and complex areas of experience, and metaphor can provide ways of simplifying complexities and making abstractions accessible and more understandable to the broad international audience. Thus, the metaphorical process serves a heuristic function by conceptualising the various and complex aspects of diplomacy and international relations such as negotiations, institutions, foreign policies, bilateral relations, global issues in terms of concrete, simpler, physical and better-defined areas of experience (Marks, 2018, p.137-138). For instance, Lakoff (2003) observed that the US foreign policy is structured by a worldview based on the conceptualisation THE WORLD IS A COMMUNITY. Within this community, there are NATIONS AS PERSONS establishing and maintaining social relationships, including *neighbours, friends, enemies, rogue states*, and so on. Being conscious of this role of metaphors allows diplomats to be aware of their own world view but also of the world view of their counterparts (Höne, 2012). This view can be crucial in intercultural communication and diplomatic translation/interpreting, especially when the languages of both parties differ in their conceptual systems.

In addition to being a heuristic device, metaphor is also an important element for communication in discourse. Diplomats need to show that besides understanding abstract concepts, they are able to communicate them. As such, metaphor is used in diplomatic discourse to communicate ideas in a vivid manner and has a persuasive function according to the context in which it is used. Charteris-Black (2011) explains that metaphor is an important tool for persuasion because it represents a novel way of viewing the world and, as a result, offers some fresh insights. Diplomats may use different metaphors to provide different representations of the same topic or event, primarily in order to persuade others to adopt the same views. For instance, the JOURNEY metaphor can be used in diplomatic discourse to create or preserve momentum of negotiations. Being *on track, racing against time*, and *step-by-step* diplomacy are some common metaphorical expressions. If the aim is to highlight the danger of failure of negotiations, metaphorical expressions such as being *derailed* or being *on a slippery slope* can be important in provoking the desired emotional response and consequently the desired action “because they draw on value systems by exploiting the associative power of language” (Charteris-Black, 2011, p.44).

III. Metaphor Translation

The shift of metaphor research from the traditional rhetorical perspective to the cognitive one has brought new insights into the study of metaphor within translation studies. It is argued that metaphor translation is not confined to the individual metaphorical expression as identified in the source text, but it becomes also linked to the level of conceptual systems. In particular, translating metaphor is best done through a correlation of conceptual metaphors and metaphorical expressions in both languages (Schäffner, 2004, p.1258; Maalej, 2008, p.61). Hence, an important consideration in metaphor translation from a cognitive approach is the identification of the mappings between the source and target domains, which allows a better understanding of a conceptual basis of metaphors and more effective translation.

On the basis of the cognitive approach, Mandelblit (1995) presented Cognitive Translation Hypothesis. She argued that the difficulty in metaphor translation “resides in the use of different metaphorical mappings between the source language and the target language to express the same idea” (p.483). In other words, the translation of metaphor involves not only the transfer of a certain linguistic representation from a certain language to another, but also, and more importantly, a transfer of a cognitive construct that represents how people conceptualise the world. Mandelblit (1995) considers two schemes of cognitive mapping conditions for the translation of metaphors:

- a) Similar Mapping Condition (SMC): it is assumed here that the linguistic metaphors both in the ST and TT correspond to the same conceptual mapping;
- b) Different Mapping Condition (DMC): in case where there is a shift between the conceptual metaphors of the two languages.

According to Mandelblit, metaphors of similar mapping condition are universal metaphors; they have similar conceptual domains in different cultures and languages. Therefore, translating these metaphors into equivalent target language metaphors is an easy and less time-consuming task, and the original conceptual metaphor can be preserved in translation. Translating the English metaphor TIME IS MONEY into Arabic as الوقت من ذهب involves mapping between the same conceptual domains in the source language and the target language. That is, the target domain TIME and the source domain of MONEY, i.e. a valuable commodity and limited resource. hence, such metaphor is preserved in translation. On the other hand, it is quite challenging and time-consuming to translate metaphors that have different mapping conditions (Mandelblit, 1995 p.493). Al-Hasnawi (2007) explained that if the SL and the TL employ different source domains to conceptualise the same metaphor, the translator has to make on the behalf of the target text reader conceptual shift through searching for the appropriate source domain in the target language. This view suggests that the larger the difference between the ways in which two language communities conceptualise similar experiences, the more challenging the task of translation may become, especially for translators who are not familiar with the host of variables affecting the selection of metaphors in a specific type of discourse.

Methodology

The study examines some metaphors used in diplomatic discourse in the specific genre of UN diplomatic speeches. A sample of English speeches delivered at 76th session of the United Nations General Assembly and their Arabic translation was selected as a corpus for the study.

The first step of the analysis consists of the identification of metaphorical expressions in the corpus using the Metaphor Identification Procedure (MIP) proposed by The Pragglejaz Group (2007), which helped us to identify metaphors in a reliable and systematic way. According to this method, the procedures for identifying metaphors in discourse can be presented as follows:

1. Speeches are read initially to establish a general understanding of content and meaning;
2. Lexical units are identified;
3. Meaning of lexical units is determined in context;
4. The status of the meaning of lexical units is made, i.e., establishing whether the lexical unit has a more basic contemporary meaning (i.e., related to embodied experience or action; more concrete or older historically);
5. If it is determined that the lexical unit has a more basic contemporary meaning in other texts/contexts compared to the context under exploration, and if the contextual meaning can be understood in comparison to this, then the lexical unit is considered as metaphorical (Pragglejaz Group, 2007, p.03).

Once the metaphorical expressions are identified with MIP, the conceptual metaphors are established and are grouped on the basis of the major types of source domains drawing on CMT framework. Next, the corresponding equivalents of these metaphors in the target text will be identified and compared according to the two schemes of Cognitive Translation Hypothesis, namely: similar mapping condition (SMC) and different mapping condition (DMC), so as to determine whether conceptual metaphors are preserved and/or transformed in diplomatic translation.

Data Analysis

The metaphorical expressions identified have been analysed in the source and target languages in terms of the two domains of conceptualisation. The analysis below discusses some examples:

1. Journey metaphor

ST Conceptual Metaphor	Metaphorical expressions in the ST	Metaphorical expressions in the TT
	We are on the <i>edge of an abyss</i> , and we are <i>moving in the wrong direction</i> .	فنحن على شفا هاوية سحيقة، وما زلنا نتحرك في الاتجاه الخطأ.

PURPOSEFUL ACTIVITIES ARE JOURNEYS	And the scientists and experts are telling us that we're fast approaching a point of no return.	إذ يخبرنا العلماء والخبراء بأننا نقترب بسرعة من نقطة اللاعودة.
	Instead of the path of solidarity , we are on a dead end to destruction.	وبدلاً من أن نسلك مسار التضامن ، ترانا على طريق مسدود آخره دمار.
	It is in line with the mandate I was given by the UN75 Declaration to seek a pathway to a better world.	وهو متناسق مع الولاية التي أسندت إلي في الإعلان الصادر بمناسبة الاحتفال بالذكرى السنوية الخامسة والسبعين لإنشاء الأمم المتحدة، لإيجاد السبيل المؤدي إلى عالم أفضل
	It lives in the young people of Zambia who harnessed the power of their vote for the first time, turning out in record numbers to denounce corruption and chart a new path for their country.	إنه يعيش في شباب زامبيا الذين سخروا قوة أصواتهم للمرة الأولى وأقبلوا بأعداد قياسية للإعلان عن شجب الفساد و رسم مسار جديد لوطنهم.

The journey metaphor is based on the experiential correlations between a physical experience (e.g., arriving at a destination), and a more abstract, subjective experience (e.g., achieving a goal) (Semino, 2008, p.92). Journey was one of the most common source domains for metaphors in the source text. This is not surprising since the diplomatic processes involve efforts towards achieving certain goals and objectives. Through journey metaphor, we find in source text that the speakers highlight aspects of the global inappropriate conditions by conceptualising them in terms of negative experiences of a journey. This was conveyed to the audience through expressions such as: **moving in the wrong direction**, being on a **dead end**, **approaching a point of no return**. On the other hand, speakers also talked about ways of achieving shared goals and overcoming challenges in terms of positive aspects of a journey through the metaphorical use of **path**, which was found in expressions such as: **path** of solidarity, **seek a pathway** to a better world, **chart a new path** for their country. These expressions evoke a sense of change and call upon for a new journey in order that positively evaluated purposes may be successfully attained.

As seen in the examples, the metaphorical expressions in Arabic translation show they are manifestations of the same conceptual metaphor of journey found in the source text. They are rendered in the target text through expressions which reflect the same semantic aspects of the source text by using literal translation. This reveals that Arabic translations denoting a journey reflect similar mapping condition (SMC) to the English source text. Thus, the

original conceptual metaphor PURPOSEFUL ACTIVITIES ARE JOURNEYS is preserved in the target text.

2. War metaphor

PANDEMIC IS A WAR	I'll be announcing additional commitments as we seek to advance the <i>fight against</i> COVID-19.	سأعلن عن التزامات إضافية بينما نسعى لتعزيز الجهود المبذولة لمكافحة كوفيد-19
	Bombs and bullets cannot <i>defend against</i> COVID-19 or its future variants.	لا يمكن للقنابل والرصاص الدفاع عن نفسها ضد فيروس كورونا أو ضد أي من متحوراته المستقبلية
	Will we work together to save lives, <i>defeat</i> COVID-19 everywhere.	سنعمل معا من أجل إنقاذ الأرواح، وهزيمة كوفيد-19 في كل مكان
	We see the vaccines developed in record time — <i>a victory</i> of science and human ingenuity.	فمن ناحية، نرى كيف تنتج اللقاحات في أوقات قياسية — وهو ما يشكل انتصاراً للعلم وللإبداع البشري

The war metaphor is generally used in diplomatic speeches in relation to particularly serious and dangerous issues (Semino, 2008, p.100). The metaphorical expressions identified in the source text that are related to war were used to represent the COVID-19 pandemic as an enemy, resulting in the conceptual metaphor PANDEMIC IS A WAR. This metaphorical way of thinking was conveyed through a range of linguistic manifestations such as: *fight against*, *defeat*, *defend against*, *victory*. The use of this particular conceptual metaphor highlights the gravity of the problem in question and can evoke a sense of fear and urgency, which in turn motivates the international audience to pay attention and take actions about this current global threat.

As it can be seen in the examples above, the Arabic target text depicts the same conceptualisation of Covid-19 as an enemy represented in the source text. All metaphorical expressions related to the war domain identified in the source text have been retained in the Arabic target text and were translated to their direct equivalents, i.e., literal translation. This points out that both source language and target language share similar mapping condition (SMC). This way, when the metaphorical expressions are retained in the target text, the original conceptual metaphor PANDEMIC IS A WAR is also preserved in translation.

3. Building metaphor

PEACE IS A BUILDING	... United Nations, broke the cycle of war and destruction and <i>laid the foundations</i> for more than seven decades of relative peace and growing global prosperity.	... أسسوا الأمم المتحدة، وكسروا الحلقة المفرغة للحرب والدمار، وأرسوا الأساس لأكثر من سبعة عقود من السلام النسبي وتنامي الازدهار العالمي.
DIPLOMATIC RELATIONS ARE BUILDINGS	I have prioritized <i>rebuilding</i> our alliances. We know how to <i>build</i> effective partnerships to dismantle terrorist networks by targeting their financing and support systems.	أعطيت الأولوية لإعادة بناء تحالفاتنا نحن نعرف كيف نبني شراكات فعالة لتفكيك الشبكات الإرهابية من خلال استهداف أنظمة التمويل والدعم الخاصة بما

The building metaphor involves the process of mapping between the conceptual source domain of building a physical entity onto the conceptual target domain of creating something abstract. Metaphors of this source domain carry in general a positive connotation and are employed to express aspiration towards desired abstract goals (Charteris-Black, 2004, p.70). Therefore, they can be metaphorically used in diplomatic discourse to conceptualise particular aspects of diplomacy which are positively evaluated. In the example above, the metaphorical expression *laid the foundations* identified in the source text is a manifestation of the conceptual metaphor PEACE IS A BUILDING. It has a strong positive connotation since it conveys a message of stability and process towards achieving long-term goals such as peace and global prosperity. Also, diplomatic processes such as partnerships and alliances, which entail structured frameworks for collaboration between states, can be better understood when conceptualised as constructions. The metaphorical expressions *build* effective partnerships, and *rebuilding* alliances were identified the source text.

It is evident from the examples above that the Arabic translations of the metaphorical expressions are part of the same cognitive domains of the source text conceptual metaphors. Peace, partnerships and alliances were also conceptualised as buildings in the Arabic target text in which the translator employed direct equivalents of the metaphorical expressions. The scheme is therefore one of a similar mapping condition (SMC) and both conceptual metaphors are preserved in translation.

4. Land metaphor

OBJECTIVES ARE THE PROMISED LAND	But <i>to reach that land of our promises</i> , we must bridge Great Divides.	لكن لكي نفي بتلك الوعود، لا بدّ لنا من سد الفجوات الكبرى التي تفصل بيننا
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In the example above, the speaker in the source text talks about objectives to be achieved, which were conceptualised in terms of a religious domain that contradict the cultural norms of the Arabic language. The metaphorical expression identified in the source text *to reach that land of our promises* has not been retained in the Arabic target text as the scheme follows different mapping condition (DMC), and thus losing the original conceptual metaphor. In order to deal with the differences in the cognitive domains and to avoid the clash with the target culture, the source text metaphorical expression was paraphrased in the target text and a non-metaphorical expression has been chosen instead: لكي نفي بتلك الوعود, which is more acceptable to the target audience. This choice conveys the intended meaning and serves the same communicative function of the original conceptual metaphor, although there is a loss of metaphoricity. This loss is justified if the target language is unable to offer equivalent conceptual metaphor.

Conclusions

This study focused on the use of metaphors in a sample of English diplomatic discourse and their corresponding translations in Arabic from a cognitive perspective. The textual analysis showed that conceptual metaphor is a major characteristic of diplomatic discourse and is manifested in a wide range of metaphorical expressions. The major types of conceptual metaphors identified in the corpus includes the source domains of WAR, JOURNEY, BUILDING, PERSON and NATURE. It has been found that metaphors used in diplomatic discourse are not optional linguistic tools to decorate the text, but are indispensable cognitive and communicative tools to construct abstract diplomatic concepts and play a crucial role in facilitating diplomatic communication.

The contrastive analysis in this study indicated that there is a high degree of similarity in terms of both conceptual metaphors and metaphorical expressions between the English source text and the Arabic target text, despite the fact that the two are distant languages and cultures. An observable majority of conceptual metaphors identified in the corpus have been preserved in translation. The tendency to preserve the same metaphorical conceptualisation of the source text can be generally attributed to the universal nature of metaphors used in diplomatic speeches across different languages, and also to the fact that diplomatic translation/interpreting require accuracy and high fidelity to the source text. This gives further evidence that translators/interpreters working in diplomatic settings are required to retain the information as much as possible when translating/interpreting diplomatic speeches, which is significant for the communicative function of the translation.

On the other hand, there were few instances where source text conceptual metaphors were transformed. Non-metaphorical expressions were preferred in the target text whenever the source domain was not considered to be adequate association or is controversial in the Arabic target culture. In such a case, the translator would give priority to the communicative sense and pay attention to the target audience expectations over preserving the original conceptual metaphor. Another observation is that the present study did not witness any case in which a conceptual metaphor was completely omitted without corresponding expressions in the target text. This further stress the fact that omission of

metaphor can seriously affect the target text in terms of conceptual significance and communicative force of discourse.

The findings of the study can have pedagogical implications for diplomatic translation/interpreting. It could be argued that including metaphor in translation/interpreting courses would increase the trainees' awareness of the cognitive and communicative roles of conceptual metaphor, which would foster their understanding of diplomatic discourse in different multilingual and multicultural environments and allow them to produce more natural and accurate equivalents when they translate metaphors found in diplomatic language.

One of the limitations of this study is the corpus size and the limited number of data analysed, which makes the current findings only indicative and may not be generalised. Therefore, there exist a need for further evidence from studies with a larger corpus to strengthen the research results.

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